

Proposal for q-factors for modern masonry buildings for EC8 Part 1

Background document for the masonry chapter in EC8 Part 1

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1 Objectives of this document

This document puts forward a proposal for revised q-factors for masonry buildings based on the available literature and on recent work by Paolo Morandi, Christoph Butenweg and Guido Magenes carried out in support of code development.

2 Reference work

In addition to the existing published literature on the specific topic of q-factors for masonry buildings, this document is based on findings and recommendations developed by Paolo Morandi, Guido Magenes and their masonry research group in Pavia [1]–[4] and the research group by Christoph Butenweg in Aachen [5]–[7]. Both research groups established large sets of reference buildings, for which the equivalent q-factors were computed on the basis of pushover analyses. All these recent analyses address unreinforced masonry buildings.

As an important premise to the discussion, two facts must be recalled, as reported in the available literature. The first is that, as stated in Magenes, 2006 [8] and recognized by any designer who has ever tried to carry out seismic safety checks via linear analysis and the set of rules included in the current EN 1996 and EN 1998 editions [9], [10] [“with a q of 1.5 or even 2, it is practically impossible to satisfy strength safety checks for any configuration of URM, 2- or 3-storey building for design $a_g S$ greater than 0.1g; in numerous cases the strength safety checks would not be satisfied even for $a_g S = 0.05g$ ”]. As it can be recalled, the product $a_g S$ represents the design acceleration spectrum ordinate at $T=0.0$ s, and a value of 0.1 g represents a common value for low hazard regions, whereas 0.05 g is representative of a very low hazard region (assuming a design return period of 475 years).

The second fact is that field surveys show that modern URM buildings with stiff slabs, walls with limited effective slenderness ratio h_{eff}/t_{eff} and good connections perform well in seismic events of significant intensity. This has been confirmed also by observation of new unreinforced masonry buildings in epicentral areas in the recent seismic events in Italy (Emilia 2012 and Central Italy sequence 2016-2017), as reported by Penna et al., 2014 [11] and Sorrentino et al., 2019 [12].

Hence, it is apparent that any sensible value of q for a newly designed masonry building where a box behaviour and redundancy is guaranteed, and the out-of-plane failure of walls is prevented, should be (significantly) larger than 2.0.

Based on the information available at the time on experimental drift capacity from laboratory tests of mostly solid brick masonry walls, the Italian norms NTC 2008 [19], drafted in 2007, were allowing a global q-factor up to 3.6 for URM masonry walls (inclusive of overstrength), later reduced to 3.0 in the NTC 2018 [20] as more data on drift capacity had become available.

In the works carried out by the research group in Pavia, the proposal of q-factor values was derived by computing pushover analyses of URM and reinforced masonry buildings using the software SAM II (Magenes et al. 2006, [13], later implemented in several commercial softwares), modelling the walls both as cantilever and as equivalent frames [1], [2], [8]. Analyses were carried out on one- to four-storey of up to eight different plan configurations. In the most recent additional work in support of this document, equivalent frame modelling were carried out on six plan layouts, considering for each configuration four wall thicknesses (24-40 cm) and 1-4 storeys, resulting therefore in total in 96 configurations. For each configuration, four pushover analyses were conducted (positive and negative direction, loading in x and y direction).

The research group in Aachen analysed 28 building configurations of terrace, single-family and multi-family buildings with 1-4 storeys [14]. They analysed each building in its weakest

direction. The pushover analyses were conducted by engineering models developed by the research group, which account for the framing action.

The displacement demand was determined by various methods. The final works by the research group in Pavia uses a modified N2-method, which uses an improved estimate of the displacement demand for short-period structures [15]. The research group in Aachen used their approach of the capacity spectrum method with overdamped spectra [5].

3 Composition of the q-factor

According to the PT1 document of the first part of EC8-Part 1 [16], the q-factor can be written as a product of three factors (Section 6.3.2 (1)):

$$q = q_D \cdot q_R \cdot q_S \quad (1)$$

where

- q_D is the behaviour factor component for the deformation capacity and energy dissipation capacity;
- q_R is the behaviour factor component accounting for overstrength due to the redistribution of seismic action effects in redundant structures;
- q_S is the behaviour factor component accounting for overstrength due to all other sources.

4 The q_D factor for masonry buildings

The q_D factor represents the deformation and energy dissipation capacity of the building. This capacity depends on many characteristics of the building, including deformation capacity of each wall, coupling of the walls through slabs and ring beams (or spandrels, when present), wall length distributions and torsional effects.

4.1 Summary of reference studies on q_D factors

In their latest study on q-factors [1], the research group of Pavia assumed the following ultimate drift capacities for the URM walls::

- shear failure: $\delta_u=0.3\%$
- flexural failure: $\delta_u=0.8\%$

i.e. the in-plane lateral force capacity of the piers drops to zero beyond those limits. It is noted that NTC 2018 explicitly provides a 0.5% NC design drift capacity for shear failures, which was derived from a 0.3% SD design capacity.

The research group of Aachen [14] assumed drift capacities given in the German National Annex to EC8 [17], which differentiate for walls failing in shear between high and low axial load ratios (ALR):

- shear failure: $ALR \leq 0.15: \delta_u=0.4\%, ALR > 0.15: \delta_u=0.3\%$
- flexural failure: $\delta_u=0.6\%$

The values above were considered by the two research groups as suitable design values as per the codes that they were referring to, i.e. not to be reduced by further safety factors (although, since statistical evaluations of the drift capacities were at that time not available, they could not be associated to any specific fractile values). The Pavia group had however carried out calculations also for lower values of drift capacities (from 0.25% to 0.4% for shear failures).

The research group of Aachen obtained for the most critical soil conditions a 5% fractile value for the q_D factor between 1.6 and 2.2 for the three building classes (terrace, single-family, multi-family building). The research group of Pavia obtained mean values between 2.30-2.95 for 2-4 storey buildings. Pavia analysed the buildings in all directions while Aachen only considered the critical (weaker) direction. Note further that the representative values given here are not based on a rigorous statistical analysis. Assuming that all analyses were governed by walls failing in shear, it is proposed to associate, as a reference for discussion, a q_D factor of 2.0 to buildings constructed with masonry typologies that have a δ_{SD}/γ_{Rd} drift capacity of 0.3% where γ_{Rd} is a safety factor.

4.2 Considerations with regard to the partial safety factor on displacements

This section provides information on the assumed drift capacities for walls failing in shear. As outlined above, it is assumed that walls failing in shear are controlling the displacement capacity of the building. This is a conservative assumption, and realistic for most practical cases.

It is here further assumed that the design displacement capacity is taken as a suitably low percentile of the drift capacities at SD. As a reference for discussion, the 5% fractile is used. These values are derived as follows:

- The median value of the ultimate drift capacity of walls failing in shear is derived based on experimental results. The experimental ultimate drift capacity is defined as the drift capacity at 20% drop in strength.
- The median drift capacity at SD is derived by multiplying the ultimate drift capacity by 3/4.
- The ratio between median value and 5% fractile value is obtained based on statistical analysis of the ultimate drift capacities of walls failing in shear. The median SD drift capacity is divided by this ratio in order to obtain the 5% fractile value of the median SD drift capacity. It is therefore assumed that the drift capacity at SD follows a similar distribution as the drift capacity at NC.

The median values of the ultimate drift capacity are summarised in Table 1; the derivation of these values is given in [18]. Included in this table are masonry typologies for which more than 10 test results for walls failing in shear were available.

The current version of EC8-Part 3 [19] assumes that SD drift capacities can be estimated as 0.75 times NC drift capacities. The statistical analysis in [18] shows that a value of $R_{SD/NC}=0.75$ corresponds in fact rather well to the median ratio of the drift at maximum resistance to the ultimate drift. In mechanical terms (and before applying the correction factors outlined below), the SD drift capacity computed as $\delta_{SD}=0.75\delta_u$ corresponds therefore approximately to the drift at maximum resistance, i.e., to the drift before strong damage localisation.

At ultimate drift, the ratio between the median value and the 5% fractile value varies between 1.6 and 2.1 (Table 1, [18]). The largest ratio is obtained for CS-masonry. However, for this masonry typology the CoV is large and the predicted 5% fractile value is smaller than any drift capacity obtained in tests ($\min(\delta_u)$). Hence, if for this masonry typology the 5% fractile value is replaced by the smallest observed value, all ratios vary between $\delta_{50\%}/\max(\delta_{5\%}, \min(\delta_u))$ 1.6 and 1.9. In the following, the average ratio of these boundary values is considered, i.e., $\gamma_{Rd}=1.75$.

The ultimate drift capacities determined in [18] can be considered conservative estimates of the drift capacity at NC for the following reasons:

- The applied loading histories contain typically a very large number of cycles, especially if referred to low to moderate seismic hazard regions [20], which are the ones where URM design is possible. In particular, walls failing in shear are sensitive to the loading

history [21]. The analysis carried out in [21] have also shown that exposing the walls to symmetric cycles, i.e., with similar amplitudes in the positive and negative direction has also adverse effects on the drift capacity. Experimentally verified is the ratio of monotonic to cyclic drift capacities (for symmetric cycles), which is for walls failing in shear around 2.0. The effect of the loading history at the NC drift capacity was therefore estimated as $R_{LH,NC}=1.2$, i.e., it is assumed that the NC drift capacity of walls subjected to loading histories as experienced in the field is at least 20% larger than those derived from the quasi-static tests currently contained in the data base. For the SD limit stage, the effect of the loading history is expected to be smaller than on the ultimate drift. For this reason, the correction factor account for the load history at the SD limit stage was reduced to $R_{LH,SD}=1.1$. Further experimental research on the effect of the loading history would be desirable.

- The NC drift capacity of a wall is set equal to the ultimate experimental drift capacity (Section 10.3 in [18]). The latter is defined as the drift at 20% drop in strength [18]. At this point, the masonry walls are still able to carry their axial load, i.e., they have not yet reached collapse. The ratio between the drift at axial load failure and the ultimate drift varies significantly between masonry typologies. Unfortunately, most tests on masonry walls stopped before axial load failure was reached. As a proxy, [18] considers the ratio between maximum recorded drift to ultimate drift. This ratio is for walls failing in shear around $R_{ALF/NC}=1.2$ (note that for AAC it is significantly lower).
- Further effects that increase the ultimate drift capacity [18], such as the shear span to wall height ratio, are not considered here because they are assumed to lead to larger ultimate drifts and yield drifts; the resulting q_d factor might therefore not be considerably affected. In almost all tests that led to shear failure the boundary conditions corresponded to double-bending conditions (shear span H_0 to wall height H ratio of 0.5). This is the boundary condition that leads to the smallest ultimate drift capacities. In fact, the ultimate drift capacities scale almost linearly with H_0/H . The coupling provided by horizontal elements is typically not sufficiently strong to impose perfect double-bending conditions.

The 5% fractile value of the drift at NC is therefore estimated as follows:

$$\delta_{NC,5\%} = \delta_{u,50\%} \cdot R_{LH,NC} \cdot \frac{R_{ALF}}{NC} \cdot \frac{1}{\gamma_{Rd}} = \delta_{u,50\%} \cdot 1.2 \cdot 1.2 \cdot \frac{1}{1.75} = \delta_{u,50\%} \cdot 0.82$$

Correspondingly, the 5% fractile value of the drift at SD is computed as:

$$\delta_{SD,5\%} = \delta_{u,50\%} \cdot \frac{R_{SD}}{NC} \cdot R_{LH,SD} \cdot \frac{R_{ALF}}{NC} \cdot \frac{1}{\gamma_{Rd}} = \delta_{u,50\%} \cdot 0.75 \cdot 1.2 \cdot 1.1 \cdot \frac{1}{1.75} = \delta_{u,50\%} \cdot 0.56$$

The ratio of the 5% fractile value of drift at NC to the 5% fractile value at SD is therefore $0.82/0.56=1.46$.

The so-obtained 5% fractile value of the drift at SD are summarised in Table 2; the drift values are rounded to the nearest 0.025. Also included in the table is the drift capacity of light-weight concrete units. For this type of units the number of tests was not sufficient to compute the standard deviation but a median value could be computed. Note that these drift capacities are valid for low to moderate axial load ratios [18].

Table 1: Statistics of ultimate drift capacity for walls failing in shear (reproduced from [18])

	# of tests	min(δ_u)	5%ile	50%ile	50%ile/5%ile	σ	CoV	50%ile/max(5%ile, min(δ_u))
		[%]	[%]	[%]		[%]		
HC	41	0.13	0.19	0.31	1.64	0.10	0.31	1.64

SB	15	0.24	0.38	0.69	1.82	0.28	0.38	1.82
CS	11	0.18	0.13	0.28	2.13	0.15	0.49	1.56
AAC	19	0.14	0.20	0.37	1.90	0.16	0.41	1.90

Table 2: Computed 50% fractile and 5% fractile values of the drift at SD, and corresponding q_D -values.

	$\delta_{SD,50\%}$	$\delta_{SD,5\%}=\delta_{SD,50\%}/\gamma_{Rd}$	q_D	q_D with $q_{D,max}=1.6$
	[%]	[%]	Linear scaling	
HC	0.30	0.175	1.2	1.2
SB	0.675	0.40	2.6	1.6
CS	0.275	0.15	1.0	1.0
AAC	0.375	0.20	1.4	1.4
Light-weight concrete units	0.30	0.175	1.2	1.2

4.2.1 Comparison with prEN1993-3, chapter 11

According to prEN1993-3 §11.4.1, the reference drift capacities at SD and NC for URM masonry piers can be associated to the values θ_u and $\theta_{u,2}$, respectively, where it is assumed $\theta_{u,2} = 4/3 \times \theta_u$. Design values for seismic assessment should be obtained dividing such capacities by a $\gamma_{Rd} = 1.7 \div 1.85$ to account for uncertainty in capacity (Table 11.7).

Table 3 summarises the values for θ_u and $\theta_{u,2}$ that are provided in the current draft of prEN1998-3 (2019) for shear failures.

Table 3: Drift values θ_u and $\theta_{u,2}$ for shear failures according to the current draft of prEN1998-3 (2019).

Type	θ_u (%)	$\theta_{u,2}$ (%)
Shear sliding pre-modern masonry	0.8	1.07
Shear, pre-modern, failure of units	0.5	0.67
Shear sliding, modern, (hollow units)	0.4	0.53
Diagonal cracking, stair-stepped crack in regular masonry	0.6	0.8
Diagonal cracking, irregular masonry	0.5	0.67

Thus, design values for SD and NC (divided by γ_{Rd}) drift capacities lie within the approximate ranges: 0.22%-0.5% for SD and 0.29%-0.63% for NC, respectively, the lowest bounds being valid for hollow units, modern masonry and $\gamma_{Rd}=1.85$ (maximum uncertainty).

4.3 Recommendations for q_D factors

Ideally, the analyses carried out by the groups in Pavia and Aachen should be repeated for various masonry typologies, accounting for their different drift capacities. As this task requires significant time and could not yet be carried out, for the moment a simple linear scaling will be applied in order to derive q -factors for unreinforced masonry typologies with a drift capacity different from $\delta_{SD}/\gamma_{Rd}=0.3\%$ for walls failing in shear. Assuming the δ_{SD} drift capacities proposed in Table 2, and assuming for $\delta_{SD}/\gamma_{Rd} = 0.3\%$ a q_D factor of 2.0, the resulting q_D factors are summarised also in Table 2. A maximum q_D value of 1.6 for URM is suggested in order to maintain a hierarchy with CM and RM, which affects the q_D value for solid brick masonry.

The linear scaling makes implicitly the assumption that the yield drift remains constant and that the equal displacement rule applies. Both assumptions are not correct; further analyses where the drift capacity and the stiffness of the masonry typologies are varied would therefore be desirable. Note that the drift capacities given in Table 1, and therefore also the derived q_D

factors in Table 2, are only applicable if all walls of the building are subjected to axial load ratios (ALR) \leq LIMIT_ALR [18]. LIMIT_ALR corresponds to the axial load ratio limit for which the given drift capacities are applicable. For larger ALRs, reduced drift capacities and therefore behaviour factors should be assumed. Such buildings should ideally be analysed by means of nonlinear analyses as outlined in EC8-Part 3 [19]. To avoid the sudden jump in drift capacities at $ALR=ALR_LIMIT$, it is recommended to use a progressive reduction, as for instance in the drift capacity model 2 in [18], which defines the drift capacity as a function of the ALR and the shear span to height ratio.

Studies on the deformation capacity of reinforced and confined masonry walls are limited in the literature, and those available refer to specific typologies. Ultimate drift capacities in the range 0.6-1.0% for shear failures and 1.25-1.5% for flexural failures were found on storey-high reinforced masonry walls [22], with reinforcement ratios close to the minimum required by EC6 and EC8 and hollow clay units. The drift capacities are hence from 50 to 100% larger than the corresponding URM typology. The final draft of EC8-Part 3 [19] recommends to estimate the deformation capacity of reinforced and confined masonry elements as 4/3 times the deformation capacity of unreinforced masonry elements (i.e. 33% larger), however the mandatory spread horizontal reinforcement in reinforced masonry, absent in confined masonry, is a better guarantee of more stable inelastic response, which justify a differentiation between reinforced and confined masonry, as also recognized in the current EC8-Part 1 [10]. Applying again the linear scaling, the q_D factors associated with reinforced and confined masonry buildings should therefore be taken larger than those for URM. A minimum 4/3 increase for confined masonry is acceptable, but given the better performance of RM a 3/2 ratio (i.e. increase of 50%) with respect to URM is recommended, as consistent with experiments and with most codes. Hence for confined masonry it is suggested to use in general a q_D factor of 1.65 and for reinforced masonry a q_D factor of 1.8 (note: RM systems for which some experimental basis is available are built in great part with hollow clay or hollow concrete units).

In principle, the q_D factor for reinforced masonry or confined masonry buildings should not be higher than the q_D factor for reinforced concrete wall buildings of ductility class 2. Given the experimental performance of reinforced masonry and of reinforced concrete wall structures, the value of $q_D = 1.3-1.4$ adopted for DC2 RC wall buildings in the current draft of prEN 1998-1-2, appears a very low value and possibly overconservative and not fully justifiable with reference to the target probability of failure of structures designed according to EC8.

5 The q_R factor for masonry buildings

The q_R factor accounts for the redistribution of seismic action effects in redundant structures and can be written as follows (Section 7.3.3.2(1) in EC8-Part 1 [16]):

$$q_R = \alpha_u / \alpha_1 \quad (2)$$

where

- α_1 is the value by which the horizontal seismic design action is multiplied, in order to first reach the flexural or shear resistance in any member in the structure, while all other design actions remain constant [23] (Annex C);
- α_u is 90% of the value by which the horizontal seismic design action is multiplied, in order to develop the full base shear capacity of the structural system, while all other design actions remain constant [23] (Annex C).

A q_R value greater than unity is possible only if the structure is redundant, but q_R is not a measure of redundancy, neither of "plastic deformation capacity". It is instead a measure of how much the internal distribution of forces calculated with a linear elastic analysis differs from

the distribution that would result in close-to-ultimate conditions accounting for all sources of nonlinearity. Masonry structures have typically many walls and are therefore highly redundant structures. The overstrength resulting from the structural redundancy should therefore be explicitly accounted for. This idea was first introduced for masonry buildings by Magenes and Morandi [2], [8] and has been implemented in the Italian codes since 2005. In the Italian code from 2008 [19], q_R factors ranging from 1.3 to 1.8 were specified depending on the number of stories and masonry typology (unreinforced or reinforced); with the latest 2018 revision of the code this value has been set to 1.5 for RM and 1.7 for URM [24] (in return q_D for URM was reduced from 2.0 to 1.75 since it was recognised that previous analyses might have assumed drift capacities for URM walls failing in shear that were too high).

The redundancy of the structural system and therefore the q_R factor is sensitive to the floor and wall plan layout, which varies largely between the European countries [25]. For this reason, the q_R factor would lend itself as a national determined parameter (NDP). Also, depending on the structural configuration, values of q_R ranging from just above 1.0 to almost 4 were reported in numerical studies [1], [2], [8], [26]. Since one objective of the revision of EC8 is to reduce the number of NDPs, approaches need to be developed that can account for the diversity of masonry construction practice across Europe [25].

5.1 Redistribution of forces and $q_R = 1.0$

One way to account for the wide range of floor plan layouts is to set q_R to 1.0 but allow redistribution of the forces between the walls, which is clearly possible only if there is redundancy. Magenes and Damiani [23] developed an approach which accounts explicitly for the limited deformation capacity when setting limits on the redistribution of forces; this approach is valid for torsionally restrained buildings and is summarized in Annex C. It is proposed that this approach is added as an alternative to the use of heuristically based q_R factors derived from the analyses of reference buildings.

5.2 Factors affecting the α_w/α_1 ratio

In order to account for the variety of masonry constructions that are common in Europe, it is proposed to consider the following characteristics when assigning q_R factors for masonry buildings; trends of q_R -factors as obtained from one parametric study are shown in Figure 1:

- Wall lengths: If all walls have the same length and are subjected to the same static and kinematic boundary conditions and to the same axial load, the q_R factor should be one. Buildings with walls of different length in one direction should therefore be assigned a higher q_R factor than buildings where all walls in one direction have approximately the same length. It is assumed that the wall length distribution in a masonry building can be quantified at the beginning of the design since it is to a great extent dictated by architectural requirements.
- Number of walls: The more walls there are, the larger is the possibility of redistribution of forces and the larger is the redundancy of the system. This, however, results in higher q_R factors only if at least one of the following conditions applies:
 - There is a good distribution of various wall lengths and it can therefore be expected that the walls reach their yield strength not simultaneously.
 - A significant coupling action exists, which leads to different axial forces in walls and therefore to different strength and yield drifts of the walls.
- Coupling action: A significant coupling action can be provided by floors/ ring beams/ spandrels. The coupling action leads to three effects that influence the q_R factor:
 - The coupling action leads to an increase or decrease in axial force in the walls when the building is subjected to horizontal loading. Those walls for which the axial force decreases are bound to reach their yield strength earlier than those walls in which the axial force increases, because the lateral wall stiffness in linear elastic models is assumed to be independent of variations in the axial

force. A significant coupling action leads therefore to a reduced elastic limit of the system and therefore to an increase in the ratio of α_u/α_1 .

- The coupling action may decrease the displacement capacity of the building because walls are more likely to fail in shear than in flexure and are subjected to smaller shear span-to-height ratios. Note that this effect leads, however, to a reduction in the q_D factor obtained from the nonlinear analyses, not the q_R factor.
- The effect of the coupling action on the strength and stiffness (and therefore also on the displacement demand) can be accounted for explicitly through the structural analysis. The analyses of both research groups confirm that the coupling action leads to smaller q_R factors than if the coupling action is neglected and the walls are modelled as cantilevers [1,2], [8], [26].

Figure 1: Sensitivity of q_R -factors as obtained from [26]. TH = Terrace house, FH = Single family house, MFH = Multi-family house.

5.3 Summary of results by research groups in Pavia and Aachen

The research group in Pavia obtained the following results with regard to the q_R factor:

- Obtained a value of $\alpha_u/\alpha_1=1.7$ (corresponds approximately to the 10%ile value)
- For buildings that are irregular in plan, this value is approximately 20% lower.
- For terrace houses, lower values were obtained. For terrace houses, however, the lower α_u/α_1 ratio was associated to the stronger direction, whereas the seismic safety assessment is governed by the weaker direction.

The research group from Aachen obtained the following results with regard to the q_R factor:

- For single family or multi family buildings an average α_u/α_1 ratio of 1.6-1.7 was obtained (minimum value obtained: 1.4) if a limited coupling action was assumed. The 5% fractile value was approximately 1.5.
- For terrace houses in the weak direction a value of 1.3 was obtained (minimum value obtained: 1.00) if a limited coupling action was assumed. The 5% fractile value was approximately 1.0. These configuration are characterized by very few walls resisting to horizontal forces.

5.4 Proposal for q_R factors

Based on the results obtained by the research groups in Pavia and Aachen and the reasoning with regard to factors that influence the q_R factor, q_R factors for URM buildings that are regular in plan and elevation are proposed and summarised in Table 4: . For buildings that are irregular in plan and/or elevation the q_R factor should be reduced by 20% (minimum value: $q = q_s$).

For buildings with flexible slabs (i.e. slabs that provide only a limited diaphragm action), the q_R factor should be set to 1.0. Such slabs should only be permitted for CM and RM but not for URM. URM buildings with flexible slabs should be designed for DC1. Designing CM with flexible slabs might lead to larger out-of-plane displacements of piers. These larger out-of-plane displacements might reduce the in-plane drift capacity of the piers. Next to setting $q_R=1.0$, the q_D -factor should therefore be reduced by 15-20% (see Table 5). This applies similarly (though to a somewhat lesser extent) also to RM buildings. RM piers are judged less sensitive to out-of-plane displacements than CM piers because of the distributed reinforcement along the length of the piers.

Table 4: Proposal for q_R factors for URM buildings that are regular in plan and elevation

Building characteristics	q_R
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 6 walls in each direction and walls have various lengths¹⁾ and • A significant coupling action is provided by floors, ring beams and/or spandrels²⁾ 	1.6
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 6 walls in each direction and walls have various lengths or • At least 4 walls in each direction and a significant coupling action is provided by floors, ring beams and/or spandrels 	1.3
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 4 walls in each direction or only walls that have all approximately the same length 	1.0
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buildings with floors that are providing only a limited diaphragm action 	1.0

1) Walls are considered to have various lengths if the ratio of the wall lengths that correspond to the 100%ile and 75%ile is at least 1.2.

2) A significant coupling action can be assumed if the stiffness of the building is at least 1.5 times as high when the coupling is considered than when it is not considered. Single storey buildings are not likely to develop a significant coupling action.

It was shown by the work of the group of Pavia that RM buildings and URM buildings with the same structural configuration tend to have slightly different α_u/α_1 ratios. Although counterintuitive, the α_u/α_1 ratio tends to be lower for RM because the effect of minimum reinforcement requirement tends to increase more α_1 than α_u .

6 The q_s factor for masonry buildings

In Section EC8-Part 1 [16] (Section 6.3.2(1) b), the q_s component is set equal to 1.5. This applies for all building configurations. The factor q_s accounts to a large extent for the material overstrength as well as for excess resistance due to unavoidable overdesign of sections (always the next larger section is chosen). For unreinforced masonry buildings, it is assumed that the q_s factor results from three sources:

- Difference in bilinear approximations used by the prEN1998-1-2 draft and the reference works where nonlinear response of buildings was studied;
- Material safety factors;
- Effects that increase the strength but are typically not accounted for when modelling masonry buildings.

In the following, these three sources are discussed and the contribution of these sources estimated.

6.1 Difference in bilinear approximations used by the EC8 and reference studies

The methods used for the bilinearisation in the reference studies for q_R and q_D are different to the one adopted by EC8. In EC8, the bilinearisation is based on the maximum force capacity (assumed to occur at SD). In the reference studies the more common method based on energy equivalence is adopted. The definition adopted by EC8 leads to a higher q_s value and a lower q_D value. This difference is typically less than 10% and is therefore neglected.

6.2 Material safety factors

The strength of unreinforced masonry (URM) elements failing in flexure results almost exclusively from the axial force (at least for the low to moderate axial load ratios that are favoured by the proposed code). The axial force in wall elements results from the weight of the structure and the coupling effect. The coupling effect leads to an increase and decrease in the elements and does not change the sum of the net axial force to which all wall elements of a storey are subjected. The estimate of the weight of the structure is not systematically biased. For this reason, if all walls would fail in flexure, the component of q_s resulting from overstrength should be set equal to unity.

For URM walls failing in shear, the capacity depends on the axial force and the assumed material properties. Morandi et al. [27] showed that the strength predicted by EC6 equations for walls failing in shear is well predicted when using mean material parameters (Figure 13 in [27]¹). The shear strength obtained with characteristic values divided by partial safety factors is therefore in average $1.25 \times \gamma_m$ -times lower than the actual shear strength. The coefficient 1.25 is the ratio between mean and characteristic strength value (as also proposed in material testing standards). The partial safety factors are NDPs; however, the minimum permitted partial safety factor for masonry in prEN1998-1-2 is $\gamma_m=1.5$, where a minimum value of 2.0 is

¹ In Figure 13 in [27], the major part of walls where the predicted shear strength with mean material strength parameters is larger than the experimentally observed consist of walls with unfilled head joints, for which an specific failure mechanism (opening of the head joints, or “gaping”) is critical. This latter aspect may call for an improvement of EC6 shear strength formulae for unfilled headjoint construction.

used in most countries. This results in a total ratio between mean and design value of 1.873-2.5.

The reduction of material strength parameters does not result in a proportional reduction of the strength of a wall (shear failures and flexural failures have different sensitivity to material strength parameters; flexural failure is less sensitive than shear failure). Similarly, the system strength will vary in function of the predominant failure mechanism. Considering that the drift ratios that dictate the values of q_D are those associated to shear failures, and assuming that in a building the system capacity is affected in great part by shear failure (typically associated to the longer and stronger walls), a safe estimate of the effect of material strength reduction from mean to design value would affect the system capacity by a factor of 1.2. Note that since the q_D -components are based on drift capacities of walls failing in shear, it would be even justified to consider only the q_S -component for walls failing in shear, resulting in a larger factor.

6.3 Effects that increase the strength but are typically not accounted for when modelling masonry buildings

The following effects that increase the force capacity of a masonry building are typically not explicitly modelled and are therefore also attributed to the q_S component:

- Coupling effect of ring beams and of spandrels (ring beams they are typically modelled as axial member and not as flexural member; masonry spandrels are often neglected); coupling provided by the flexural stiffness of floors out of their plane;
- Flange effects, i.e. composite action of orthogonal walls intersecting at vertical edges, and kinematic effects associated to uplifting (rocking) of walls failing in flexure with limited axial force.

The magnitude of this effect will vary significantly between buildings and models. It is assumed that the contribution to q_S is in the order of at least 1.1-1.2, the lower value when coupling of ring beams or floors is explicitly modelled, the larger value when they are neglected in the model.

6.4 Summary

On the basis of these assumptions, a total q_S component of 1.35-1.5 can be justified for URM buildings in conjunction with a q_D dictated by shear failure, depending on whether the flexural coupling given by ring beams or floors is explicitly modelled or not. The 1.5 value can be adopted for reinforced and confined masonry buildings, similarly to other construction typologies.

7 Consideration of probabilistic analyses present in the literature.

Considering that the target annual probability of collapse for an ordinary building designed according to prEN1998-1-2 is $p_f=2 \times 10^{-4}$, it is of interest to look at works in the literature where probabilistic seismic assessment was carried out. In recent years an extensive coordinate project to evaluate the seismic risk of code-conforming buildings was carried out in Italy [28]–[31], with reference to the Italian norms NTC of 2008. In such study, the p_f of URM masonry buildings designed following different methods of analysis (namely linear elastic with q -factor or nonlinear static) were calculated. The buildings were “just designed” for the different seismic hazard levels and site conditions. NTC 2008 was assuming large values of q for URM ($=3.6$ for two- and three-storey, as a result of a $q_D=2.0$ and $\alpha_u/\alpha_1 = 1.8$), resulting from an estimate of ultimate deformation capacity of URM walls which were essentially based on older experiments on solid brick URM walls. In fact, in the probabilistic work the median drift capacity at NC of URM walls was assumed equal to 0.54%, and the assumed standard deviation was producing (lognormal distribution) a 5%percentile of would result in 0.35% drift, Without considering the cases of the site with very low seismic hazard (site of Milano) where the

computed p_f was too low to be meaningful, the cases of URM buildings designed with linear analysis and q-factor and no force redistribution p_f values ranging from 1.0×10^{-5} to 3.6×10^{-5} were found (Table 4).

Table 4: Annual probability of collapse for URM buildings designed with linear analysis as per NTC 2008 [28], [30]

Site	Caltanissetta	Rome	Naples
Soil type	A	A	A
$S_a(T_1)_{475}$	0.19 g	0.28 g	0.40 g
Building 2 (3 storeys)	1.79×10^{-5}	-	-
Building 8 (2 storeys)	-	-	3.64×10^{-5} (*)
Building 8 (3 storeys)	1.13×10^{-5}	1.45×10^{-5}	-
Building 9 (2 storeys)	-	1.01×10^{-5}	-
Building 9 (3 storeys)	2.97×10^{-5}	-	-

(*) Capacity/demand ratio in linear design = 0.96

Studies where lower drift capacities are used both for design and for the probabilistic assessment, in line with the more recent experimental results on modern masonry (e.g. hollow units) are still under way. However, as a first approximation it can be assumed that for the same model of building, with the same initial elastic period, a proportional reduction of ultimate drift capacity and of the q-factor used for design would lead to similar p_f values. This would hold for instance for a median drift capacity at NC of 0.4% and a corresponding q factor of 2.7, or of drift capacity 0.3% and a q factor of 2.0. It should be recalled however, as written in the introduction to this report, how a linear design with a q factor of 2.0 is recognized to lead to unrealistically conservative results, which is also consistent with the fact that the p_f that we are referring to is one order of magnitude smaller than the target probability of 2×10^{-4} . This leads again to support the use of total q factors greater than 2.0 for linear elastic design of DC2 URM buildings.

8 Conclusions and recommendations

This report puts forward proposals for the three behaviour factor components q_s , q_D and q_R of masonry buildings. It focuses on unreinforced masonry buildings but makes also recommendations for reinforced masonry and confined masonry buildings.

8.1 Summary of results presented in this study

q_s factor:

- For unreinforced masonry a q_s factor of 1.35 is obtained.
- For reinforced and confined masonry, the common q_s factor of 1.5 can be assumed.

q_D factor:

- Based on the drift capacities of unreinforced masonry walls failing in shear, q_D factors that account for the masonry typology are put forward. They are limited to buildings where the ALR of all walls is less than LIMIT_ALR. The ALR must not only account for the axial force resulting from gravity loads but also for axial loads resulting from the coupling of walls by slabs, ring beams and/or spandrels.
- Only the q_D factor for a drift capacity of 0.3% was obtained through numerical analyses. The q_D factors for other drift capacities were obtained by linear scaling. The modifications of the q-factors for different masonry typologies are therefore only first estimates. They should be validated/corrected considering results from nonlinear analyses.

q_R factor:

- A proposal for q_R factors is challenging to derive because of the diversity of building configurations across Europe.
- For this reason, q_R factors have been put forward in the attempt to capture the structural redundancy of the structure by considering three factors
 - the number of walls in one direction;
 - the distribution of wall lengths;
 - the coupling action provided by slabs, ring beams and spandrels.
- Based on these three criteria q_R factors between 1.0 and 1.6 are proposed.
- The q_R factor is reduced by 20% if the building is irregular in plan or elevation, but the q -factor does not need to be taken smaller than q_S .
- As an alternative approach, q_R factor can be set to 1.0 and the forces be redistributed between the walls within certain bounds. The bounds account for the deformation capacity of the elements.

8.2 Proposed simplifications

As outlined above, for URM buildings failing in shear a q_S factor of 1.35 is obtained. Traditionally, the q_S factor for all types of structures is set to 1.5. For design, the individual values of q_S , q_R and q_D are not relevant but their product. To avoid singling out URM buildings with different q_S values than for all other structures, it is therefore suggested to

- Increase the q_S factor for URM buildings from 1.35 to 1.5.
- Decrease the q_R factors by 1.35/1.5. A q_R factor of 1.6 therefore becomes 1.4 and a q_R factor of 1.3 becomes 1.2. The q_R factor of 1.0 is not reduced because a q_R factor smaller than 1.0 would be physically not meaningful and the so-obtained maximum q -factors seem still reasonable.

8.3 Summary of proposed q factors

The results presented in this report and the simplifications proposed in the previous section lead to maximum q-factors that are summarised in Table 5. The maximum q-factors that can be considered in design are limited to 2.8, 3.4 and 3.8 for URM, CM and RM, respectively.

Table 5 Summary of q_R , q_D and maximum q-values for various types of building configurations

Structural configuration in the earthquake direction	q_R	Masonry type	q_D	q_{max}
At least 6 piers of various lengths and a significant coupling effect	1.4	URM (general)	1.2	2.6
	1.4	Calcium silicate (hollow and solid)	1.0	2.2
	1.4	AAC Gr 1 and 1s	1.4	2.8
	1.4	URM Gr 1 and 1s clay	1.6	2.8
	1.4	Confined masonry (general)	1.65	3.4
	1.4	Reinforced masonry (general)	1.8	3.8
At least 6 piers of various lengths, or at least 4 walls and a significant coupling effect	1.2	URM (general)	1.2	2.1
	1.2	Calcium silicate (hollow and solid)	1.0	1.8
	1.2	AAC Gr 1 and 1s	1.4	2.5
	1.2	URM Gr 1 and 1s clay	1.6	2.8
	1.2	Confined masonry (general)	1.65	2.9
	1.2	Reinforced masonry (general)	1.8	3.2
Less than 6 piers of various lengths or axial load ratios, and no significant coupling effect;	1.0	URM (general)	1.2	1.8
	1.0	Calcium silicate (hollow and solid)	1.0	1.5
	1.0	AAC Gr 1 and 1s	1.4	2.1
	1.0	URM Gr 1 and 1s clay	1.6	2.4
	1.0	Confined masonry (general)	1.65	2.5
	1.0	Reinforced masonry (general)	1.8	2.7
Buildings with flexible diaphragms (confined and reinforced masonry only; URM buildings with flexible diaphragms must be designed for DC1)	1.0	Confined masonry	1.35	2.0
	1.0	Reinforced masonry	1.6	2.40

- 1) Walls are considered to have various lengths if the ratio of the wall lengths that correspond to the 100%ile and 75%ile is at least 1.2.
- 2) A significant coupling action can be assumed if the stiffness of the building is at least 1.5 times as high when the coupling is considered than when it is not considered. Single storey buildings are not likely to develop a significant coupling action.

8.4 Outlook and needs of further research

Drafting of a design code is always a balance between scientific evidence and engineering judgment. Any new code calls therefore for further studies. The following is a non-conclusive list with regard to topics related to the q-factors of masonry buildings that should be investigated in future studies:

- Risk studies of buildings designed according to these rules: Risk studies should be conducted for buildings that are designed according to these rules and following the different construction practices across Europe.
- q_D -factors for URM walls: The q_D -factors for URM walls were derived on a statistical evaluation of available tests on URM walls. Such a database should be continuously

expanded and also factors such as the influence of the load history should be studied experimentally in order to complement the numerical study conducted in preparation of this code [21]. Furthermore, the q_D -factors were only derived for one drift capacity and then linearly extrapolated to others. This is a rather crude approximation. Therefore, studies investigating explicitly the change in q_D -factor with drift capacity should be conducted.

- q_D -factors for RM and CM: Experimental research on the deformation capacity of RM and CM walls is scarce and has not been systematically reviewed for this work; i.e., the q_D -factors for RM and CM have been estimated based on the values derived for URM walls. In the future, existing experimental research on RM and CM walls should be systematically reviewed, additional experimental research carried out and q_D -factors explicitly derived for RM and CM construction.
- Influence of the spectral shape: The numerical analyses showed that the q -factors are rather sensitive to the spectral shape (i.e., the soil conditions). It could therefore be argued that the q -factor should be a function of the soil conditions. However, since such refinement is not adopted for other construction materials, it was also not introduced here but it is recommended to investigate this topic in the future.

9 References

- [1] P. Morandi, "Synthesis report on evolution of the evaluation of the q -factor for masonry buildings," Pavia, Italy, 2018.
- [2] P. Morandi, "New proposals for simplified seismic design of masonry buildings," University of Pavia, Italy, Pavia, Italy, 2006.
- [3] S. Frumento, G. Magenes, P. Morandi, and G. M. Calvi, "Interpretation of experimental shear tests on clay brick masonry walls and evaluation of q -factors for seismic design," Pavia, Italy, 2009.
- [4] K. Breis, "Verifica del fattore di struttura e del criterio dell'edificio semplice nell'Eurocodice 8 tramite analisi non lineari per la progettazione sismica di edifici in muratura," Master thesis in Civil Engineering (Supervisors: G. Magenes, P. Morandi), University of Pavia, Italy, 2018.
- [5] M. Mistler, C. Butenweg, E. Fehling, and J. Stürz, "Verformungs-basierte seismische Bemessung von Mauerwerksbauten auf Grundlage zyklischer Schubwandversuche," *Bauingenieur*, vol. 82, pp. S3–S11, 2007.
- [6] C. Butenweg and C. Gellert, "Nichtlinearer Erdbebennachweis von Mauerwerksbauten," in *SIA D 0231 "Erdbeben und Mauerwerk"*, 2009.
- [7] C. Butenweg, C. Gellert, L. Reindl, and K. Meskouris, "A nonlinear method for the seismic safety verification of masonry buildings," in *2nd International Conference on Computational Methods in Structural Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 2009.
- [8] G. Magenes, "Masonry building design in seismic areas: Recent experiences and prospects from a European standpoint," in *1st European Conference on Earthquake Engineering and Seismology (Keynote lecture)*, 2006, no. September, pp. 1–22.
- [9] CEN, "EN 1996-1-1:2005 Eurocode 6: Design of masonry structures - Part 1-1: General rules for reinforced and unreinforced masonry structures," Comité Européen de Normalisation, 2005.
- [10] CEN, "EN 1998-1: 2004 Eurocode 8: Design of structures for earthquake resistance - Part 1: General rules, seismic actions and rules for buildings," Comité Européen de Normalisation, 2004.

- [11] A. Penna, P. Morandi, M. Rota, C. F. Manzini, F. da Porto, and G. Magenes, "Performance of masonry buildings during the Emilia 2012 earthquake," *Bull. Earthq. Eng.*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 2255–2273, 2014.
- [12] L. Sorrentino, S. Cattari, F. da Porto, G. Magenes, and A. Penna, "Seismic behaviour of ordinary masonry buildings during the 2016 central Italy earthquakes," *Bull. Earthq. Eng.*, vol. 17, no. 10, pp. 5583–5607, 2019.
- [13] G. Magenes, M. Remino, C. Manzini, P. Morandi, and D. Bolognini, "SAM II, Software for the Simplified Seismic Analysis of Masonry buildings." University of Pavia and EUCENTRE, 2006.
- [14] C. Butenweg, "Skype call with Christoph Butenweg, Paolo Morandi and KB on 29.11.2018," 2018.
- [15] G. Guerrini, F. Graziotti, A. Penna, and G. Magenes, "Improved evaluation of inelastic displacement demands for short-period structures," *Earthq. Eng. Struct. Dyn.*, vol. 46, no. 9, pp. 1411–1430, 2017.
- [16] CEN, "EN 1998-1 SC8-Evolution of PT1 document: Eurocode 8: — Design of structures for earthquake resistance — Part 1: General rules, seismic actions and rules for buildings," Brussels, Belgium, 2018.
- [17] DIN, "DIN EN 1998-1/NA: 2011- 01: National Annex – Nationally determined parameters – Eurocode 8. Design of structures for earthquake resistance – Part 1: General rules, Seismic actions and rules for buildings," Berlin, Germany, 2011.
- [18] K. Beyer, B. Wilding, and A. Rezaie, "Drift capacity models for modern URM walls for EC8 Part 1," Lausanne, Switzerland, 2019.
- [19] CEN, "Eurocode 8: Design of structures for earthquake resistance - Part 3: Assessment and retrofitting of buildings and bridges (Final Draft)," Brussels, Belgium, 2017.
- [20] P. E. Mergos and K. Beyer, "Loading protocols for European regions of low to moderate seismicity," *Bull. Earthq. Eng.*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 2507–2530, Mar. 2014.
- [21] B. V. Wilding, K. M. Dolatshahi, and K. Beyer, "Influence of load history on the force-displacement response of in-plane loaded unreinforced masonry walls," *Eng. Struct.*, vol. 152, 2017.
- [22] G. Magenes, G. Calvi, and F. Gaia, "Shear tests on reinforced masonry walls," Pavia, Italy, 1996.
- [23] G. Magenes, "Proposal for q-factor design rev 2017-08-08 (draft of code sections)," Pavia, Italy, 2017.
- [24] NTC, "Decreto Ministeriale 17/01/2018: Norme tecniche per le costruzioni. Ministry of Infrastructures and Transportations," Italy, 2018.
- [25] S. Lu *et al.*, "Next generation of Eurocode 8, masonry chapter," in *Brick and Block Masonry: Trends, Innovations and Challenges - Proceedings of the 16th International Brick and Block Masonry Conference, IBMAC 2016*, 2016.
- [26] C. Butenweg, T. Kubalski, and J. Rosin, "DIBt-Project: Improved seismic design concepts for masonry buildings in Germany (Revision 1)," 2019.
- [27] P. Morandi, L. Albanesi, F. Graziotti, T. L. Piani, A. Penna, and G. Magenes, "Development of a dataset on the in-plane experimental response of URM piers with bricks and blocks," *Constr. Build. Mater.*, vol. 190, pp. 593–611, 2018.
- [28] I. Iervolino, A. Spillatura, and P. Bazzurro, "Seismic Reliability of Code-Conforming Italian Buildings," *J. Earthq. Eng.*, vol. 22, no. sup2, pp. 5–27, Dec. 2018.
- [29] P. Franchin, L. Ragni, M. Rota, and A. Zona, "Modelling Uncertainties of Italian Code-Conforming Structures for the Purpose of Seismic Response Analysis," *J. Earthq. Eng.*,

vol. 22, no. sup2, pp. 1964–1989, Dec. 2018.

- [30] C. F. Manzini *et al.*, “Masonry Italian Code-Conforming Buildings. Part 1: Case Studies and Design Methods,” *J. Earthq. Eng.*, vol. 22, no. sup2, pp. 54–73, Dec. 2018.
- [31] S. Cattari, D. Camilletti, S. Lagomarsino, S. Bracchi, M. Rota, and A. Penna, “Masonry Italian Code-Conforming Buildings. Part 2: Nonlinear Modelling and Time-History Analysis,” *J. Earthq. Eng.*, vol. 22, no. sup2, pp. 2010–2040, Dec. 2018.

10 Annex A: Extracts from the EN 1998-1 SC8-Evolution of PT1 document [16]

6.3.2 Reduced spectrum for the force-based approach

(1) In the force-based approach, the seismic action should take the form of a reduced spectrum, derived from the elastic response spectrum by introducing the behaviour factor q , which accounts for overstrength, deformation capacity and energy dissipation capacity and is given by Formula (6.2).

$$q = q_R q_S q_D \quad (6.2)$$

where:

q_R is the behaviour factor component accounting for overstrength due to the redistribution of seismic action effects in redundant structures;

q_S is the behaviour factor component accounting for overstrength due to all other sources;

q_D is the behaviour factor component accounting for the deformation capacity and energy dissipation capacity.

(2) EN 1998 is conceived in such a way that behaviour factor component values should be as given

in a) to c):

a) $q_R = 1$ if not otherwise specified in the relevant part of EN 1998. For buildings, q_R is specified in 7.3.3.1;

b) $q_S = 1,5$;

c) $q_D = 1$ for DC1.

NOTE An exception to the generic rule $q_S = 1,5$ is possible when dealing with specific devices that are designed so as to have no intrinsic overstrength, like fuse devices.

(3) Other q_D values are controlled by the ductility classes. DC2 values ~~should~~ may not be lower than 1 and DC3 values not lower than DC2 ones. q_D values should be taken as those given in the various Parts of EN 1998 ~~are given~~ for various materials and structural systems according to the relevant ductility classes ~~in the various Parts of EN 1998~~. According to 4.4.1(1)P, they should be selected so as to keep a significant margin with respect to the NC deformation capacity.

(4) q_D values may be different in different horizontal directions, although the ductility class should be the same in all directions.

11 Annex B: Extracts from the final draft of Eurocode 8-Part 3 [19]

11.4.1.2 In-plane deformation capacities of masonry elements

11.4.1.2.1 General

- (1) The deformation capacities, in terms of drift ratio, of unreinforced masonry piers and spandrels are given in 11.4.1.2.2, 11.4.1.2.3 and 11.4.1.2.4, for elements failing in flexure, shear sliding and diagonal cracking respectively.
- (2) The deformation capacities of reinforced masonry and confined masonry piers and spandrels should be obtained by amplifying the ones for unreinforced masonry by a factor 4/3, provided that details are compatible with those in EN 1996-1-1:2003, 8.2 for reinforced masonry and 8.4 for confined masonry.

12 Annex C: Proposal for redistribution of forces [23]

(4) The the behaviour factor q shall be derived for each design direction as follows:

$$q = q_0 \alpha_u / \alpha_1 \quad (9.1)$$

where:

q_0 is the basic value of the behaviour factor, dependent on the type of the structural system and on its regularity in elevation

α_1 and α_u are defined as follows:

α_1 is the value by which the horizontal seismic design action is multiplied in order to first reach the flexural or shear resistance in any member in the structure, while all other design actions remain constant;

α_u is 90% of the value by which the horizontal seismic design action is multiplied, in order to develop the full base shear capacity of the structural system, while all other design actions remain constant. The factor α_u may be obtained from a nonlinear static (pushover) global analysis.

For types a) to c) the ranges of permissible values of the upper limit value of the basic value of the behaviour factor q_0 for buildings regular in elevation are given in Table 9.1.

Table 9.1: Types of construction and upper limit of the basic value q_0 of the behaviour factor

Type of construction	Factor q_0
Unreinforced masonry in accordance with EN 1996 alone (recommended only for low seismicity cases).	1,5
Unreinforced masonry in accordance with EN 1998-1	1,5-2,0
Confined masonry	2,0-3,0
Reinforced masonry	2,5-3,0

NOTE 1 The upper limit values ascribed to q_0 for use in a country (within the ranges of Table 9.1) may be found in its National Annex. The recommended values are the lower limits of the ranges in Table 9.1.

NOTE 2. The type of construction and the relevant upper limit of the q factor could be further differentiated depending on the type of units and type of head- and bedjoints used in the construction. Such further differentiation can be given in the National Annex.

NOTE 3 For buildings constructed with masonry systems which provide an enhanced ductility of the structure, specific values of the behaviour factor q may be used, provided that the system and the related values for q are verified experimentally. The values ascribed to q for use in a country for such buildings may be found in its National Annex of this document.

(5) If the building is non-regular in elevation (see 4.2.3.3) the q_0 values listed in Table 9.1 should be reduced by 20%, but need not be taken less than $q_0 = 1,5$ (see 4.2.3.1(7) and Table 4.1).

The value of the α_u / α_1 ratio to be used in design is subject to limitations, in dependence of the use of redistribution of forces (as described in §9.4).

- a) If α_u / α_1 ratio has been obtained by a nonlinear (static) pushover analysis, no redistribution of forces is possible.
- b) If α_u / α_1 is assumed to be 1.0, redistribution according to the rules given in 9.4.- 9.4(10). is admitted.
- c) When the ratio α_u / α_1 has not been evaluated through an explicit calculation, $\alpha_u / \alpha_1 = 1.1$ can be assumed, and redistribution of forces is possible according to rule 9.4.-9.4(11)... National Annexes can provide specific values for masonry systems which provide an enhanced ductility of the structure (see Note 3 above).

9.4 Structural analysis

(1)P The structural model for the analysis of the building shall represent the stiffness properties of the entire system.

(2)P The stiffness of the structural elements shall be evaluated taking into account both their flexural and shear flexibility and, if relevant, their axial flexibility. Uncracked elastic stiffness may be used for linear analysis or, preferably and more realistically, cracked stiffness in order to account for the influence of cracking on deformations and to better approximate the slope of the first branch of a bilinear force-deformation model for the structural element.

(3) In the absence of an accurate evaluation of the stiffness properties, substantiated by rational analysis, the effective cracked bending and shear stiffness for linear analysis may be taken as one half of the gross section uncracked elastic stiffness.

(4) In the structural model masonry spandrels may be taken into account as coupling beams between two wall elements if they are regularly bonded to the adjoining walls and connected both to the floor tie beam and to the lintel below.

(5) If the structural model takes into account the coupling beams, or the coupling effect of floors or ring beams, a frame analysis may be used for the determination of the action effects in the vertical and horizontal structural elements.

(6) The shear force and bending moment in the various walls, as obtained by the linear analysis described in Section 4, can be subjected to redistribution among the walls, subject to limitations depending on the assumed ratio α_u / α_1 (see 9.2(5)).

(7) Whenever redistribution is carried out, global equilibrium must be satisfied (i.e. the same total storey shear and position of the force resultant is achieved);

(8) The consequences of the redistribution for the diaphragm(s) are taken into account.

(9) when flexible diaphragms are used, redistribution is allowed only among walls that are lying in the same vertical plane and are connected at each floor and roof level with efficient tie-beams which can resist axial tension or compression. .

(10) When the α_u/α_1 ratio is assumed to be equal to 1.0, the redistribution can be carried out so that the increase of shear in any wall is not greater than:

$$\Delta V_{max} = V \frac{\theta_{lim} \cdot h_{min} - \theta \cdot h}{\theta \cdot h} = V \left(\frac{\theta_{lim} \cdot h_{min}}{\theta \cdot h} - 1 \right) \quad (9.2)$$

where

V is the shear force obtained by the linear analysis described in section 4 in the wall where the shear force is incremented

θ is the largest chord rotation in the same wall, calculated from the linear analysis

θ_{lim} is the maximum ultimate conventional chord rotation admitted for a wall failing in shear (suggested values: for urm, ... for confined masonry, for reinforced masonry).

h is the height of the wall in which the shear force is incremented

h_{min} is the height of the shortest wall in the storey

NOTE: All quantities in equation 9.2 should be evaluated from a linear analysis in which elements are assumed to have cracked bending and shear stiffness.

(11) When a ratio α_u/α_1 greater than 1.0 is assumed, and no explicit evaluation through static nonlinear analysis has been made, force redistribution can be carried out so that the increase of shear in any wall is not greater than:

$$\Delta V_{max} = 0.2 V \quad (9.3)$$

where

V is the shear force obtained by the linear analysis described in section 4, in the wall where the shear force is incremented.

(12) No force redistribution is allowed when the α_u/α_1 ratio has been obtained by a nonlinear (static) pushover analysis